

Association between salivary lactate dehydrogenase levels and nicotine dependence score in smokeless tobacco users with gingivitis - A biochemical analysis

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Abstract

Aim: To estimate and correlate the levels of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) as salivary biomarker and nicotine dependence score in smokeless tobacco users with and without gingivitis.

Materials and Method: A total of two hundred and twenty two individuals were selected and divided into two different groups in this cross-sectional study and 5 ml of unstimulated saliva was collected by spitting method and sent for biochemical analysis to estimate levels of lactate dehydrogenase. Nicotine dependence score was determined using Fagerstrom Nicotine Dependence Scale – Smokeless Tobacco (FTND-ST).

Statistical analysis used: Descriptive statistics, One-way ANOVA and Pearsons correlation.

Results: The data presents the mean value of lactate dehydrogenase in test group 1 and test group 2 as 380.67 ± 94.84 IU/L and 660.51 ± 181.3 IU/L respectively, which was statistically significant with p value < 0.001 . LDH levels increased in individuals with gingivitis compared to the periodontally healthy group. The correlation between the parameters lactate dehydrogenase IU/L & Nicotine dependence score showed a good positive correlation and was significant with a p value of < 0.001 .

Conclusions: Salivary LDH and its association with nicotine dependence score could be a prognostic biomarker in identifying the individuals with higher risk at a very early stage. The method being noninvasive, inexpensive, and simple can be used as a screening test and can help in educating patients about the detrimental effects of tobacco.

Key-words: *Salivary lactate dehydrogenase, Smokeless tobacco, Gingivitis, Biomarkers, Nicotine*

Introduction:

Periodontal disease is caused by plaque and influenced by multiple factors which contribute in the pathogenesis and progression of the disease.¹ Tobacco consumption a risk factor, can modify the periodontal response to microbial aggression.² The two means of tobacco usage products namely smoking bidis, cigarettes, etc. and smokeless tobacco products have been studied and examined throughout the world with the practice of smokeless tobacco being common. Smokeless tobacco use has been found to have detrimental effects on periodontal health.

Smokeless tobacco (SLT) is defined as a product that contains tobacco, is not burned or smoked at the time of use, and commonly consumed nasally or orally. The enormous and widespread use of SLT dates back to the early 16th century due to its recognized properties of increasing salivation, decreasing thirst and appetite, providing therapeutic purposes and even reducing dependence on smoked tobacco.³

SLT is commercially available as gutka, containing areca nut, slaked lime and spices and more nicotine content than cigarette.⁴ India sums up for 70% of the global burden of smokeless tobacco.⁵ Tobacco chewers have an incidence of gingivitis and gingival bleeding that is similar to the incidence among non-users. The activation of patient's host response liberates multitude of metabolic byproducts at the interface between the tooth and the gingival sulcus which results into release of destructive cellular enzymes, cytokines, chemokines, and other mediators of tissue destruction.⁶ There are several markers in saliva which have been proposed and used as diagnostic tests for periodontal disease however, the diagnostic tests should demonstrate sensitivity and specificity.

The saliva contains a wide variety of proteins and enzymes with significant oral biological functions. Emerging evidence suggests that the estimation and correlation of salivary biomarkers can provide valuable indicators of periodontal disease severity and progression. Saliva, as a diagnostic fluid, contains various biomarkers that reflect the local and systemic changes occurring in response to periodontal disease. Among these biomarkers, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) has shown promise in assessing periodontal tissue damage and inflammation.

The effect of smokeless tobacco (SLT) has attained remarkably less attention as a contributing factor for periodontal disease compared to smoking. There is no study done in the literature to assess and compare periodontal status of smokeless tobacco users in association with salivary lactate dehydrogenase levels and its correlation with nicotine dependence. Hence this study was done to estimate and compare the salivary lactate dehydrogenase levels of smokeless tobacco users with and without gingivitis and its association with nicotine dependence score .

The study involved a comprehensive analysis of salivary samples from smokeless tobacco users with gingivitis, comparing their biomarker levels to periodontally healthy individuals having smokeless tobacco using habit. By analyzing salivary biomarkers, we aimed to determine if there was a significant difference in lactate dehydrogenase levels among the different groups and its correlation with nicotine dependence, consequently emphasising the potential role of smokeless tobacco in exacerbating periodontal inflammation and tissue destruction.

Materials and Methods:

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Periodontology, Faculty of Dental Science, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, after attaining approval from the institutional ethical committee. A total of 222 participants were included in the study fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria, having age in the range of 18-55 years. They were divided into following groups with required sample in each group were 111 participants based on the power analysis having 1% alpha error, 95% power of the study and a clinically significant difference of 50 units.

Test Group 1 (n=111): Periodontally healthy individuals with sulcus depth ≤ 3 mm with no attachment loss and Bleeding on Probing (BOP) (as per gingival index by Loe and Sillness 1963) with smokeless tobacco using habit.

Test Group 2 (n=111): Comprised of generalized biofilm-induced gingivitis individuals with sulcus depth ≤ 3 mm with no attachment loss but presence of BOP (as per gingival index by Loe and Sillness 1963) having smokeless tobacco consuming habit.

Nicotine dependence was determined on the basis of Fagerstrom Nicotine Dependence Scale – Smokeless Tobacco (FTND-ST). A score of 5 or more indicated a significant dependence, while a score of 4 or less showed a low to moderate dependence.

Collection of saliva sample and biochemical analysis:

Participants who agreed were included in the study and written consent was obtained from them for the study. After a detailed dental examination the individuals were allotted either in Test group 1 or Test group 2. The participants were rescheduled next day in morning from 9:00 am to 12 noon, atleast one hour after the last meal to standardize the collection according to the circadian rhythm. Desired 5 ml quantity of salivary sample was collected by spitting technique. The saliva samples were transported to the laboratory for estimation of salivary LDH immediately using standard gel coolant pack in order to maintain the temperature between 2 °C to 4 °C. Biochemical assay of saliva samples were carried out using Lactate dehydrogenase in vitro diagnostic kit (AGAPPE), in the Department of Biochemistry, Dr. N D Desai Medical College, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, Gujarat, India. Prepared solution was analyzed in semi automatic biochemical analyzer machine (Erba Mannheim Chem 5x) from which digital readings were obtained and recorded.

Statistical Tests:

Apart from Descriptive Statistics, one way ANOVA was used to assess the difference between the levels of salivary lactate dehydrogenase with respect to different groups. Pearsons correlation was done to correlate the nicotine dependence score and the LDH levels. The statistical analysis was undertaken at 95% confidence level with statistical significance at p value < 0.05.

Results:

Mean values of Nicotine dependence score distribution amongst periodontally healthy subjects (Test group 1), and subjects with gingivitis (Test group 2) with smokeless tobacco using habit are 4.41 ± 1.5 and 5.83 ± 1.5 respectively. The mean value of LDH in test group 1 and test group 2 in this study was found to be 380.67 ± 94.84 and 660.51 ± 181.3 IU/L respectively, giving statistically significant result with p value < 0.001 as shown in Table 1. The salivary LDH levels increased in individuals with gingivitis compared to the periodontally healthy group having smokeless tobacco using habit. The correlation between the parameters LDH (IU/L) & Nicotine dependence score in Test group 1 showed a moderate positive correlation, and was significant with a p value of < 0.001, whereas in Test group 2 showed a good positive correlation and was significant with a p value of < 0.001 as shown in Graph 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: One way ANOVA

	Age (years)	LDH (IU/L)
Test Group 1(111)	24.94±5.15	380.67±94.84
Test Group 2(111)	27.05±6.47	660.51±181.3
F	271.578	121.668
P value	<0.001	<0.001

One way ANOVA shows P value < 0.001

Table 2: Pearsons correlation to correlate the LDH levels and Nicotine Dependence score in both the groups

TEST GROUP	PARAMETERS BEING CORRELATED	N	Correlation(r)	P VALUE
1	LDH (IU/L) & Nicotine dependence score	111	0.316	<0.001
2	LDH (IU/L) & Nicotine dependence score	111	0.566	<0.001

Table 3: Mean value of Nicotine dependence score in Test group 1 and Test group 2

		N	MEAN±SD	MEDIAN (IQR)	RANGE (Min-Max)
Nicotine dependence score	Test Group 1	111	4.41±1.5	4(4,5)	1 to 8
	Test Group 2	111	5.83±1.5	6(5,7)	3 to 9

Graph 1: Pearsons correlation between LDH levels and Nicotine dependence score

Discussion:

Tobacco stimulates⁷ the body to generate more free radicals that are endogenously produced in various cellular metabolic activities which play a role in preventing microbial pathogen invasion at low concentrations. However, as their concentration rises, they may damage cellular components, eventually causing denaturation or mutation, which can be seen in parasitic infections, inflammatory diseases and cancer.¹¹ Smokeless tobacco products are extremely addictive due to their high nicotine content.

Biochemical tests are introduced and are highly preferred tool for diagnosis and treatment planning for diseases that have an apparent metabolic basis and those in which biochemical alterations are a result of the disease. Human saliva mimics blood in various biological aspects. Moreover, it follows a simple and non-invasive collection method with low-cost and easy storage nature when compared with gingival crevicular fluid (GCF).

Periodontal destruction has been seen more in tobacco chewers when compared to smokers and non-tobacco users. This may be due to the cumulative effect of placement of tobacco for prolonged period of time in the oral cavity and also more irritants seen in smokeless tobacco products.⁸ Presence of LDH in extracellular tissues is related to cell necrosis and tissue breakdown, which is seen in periodontal diseases as well as tobacco users. Hence, the present study was planned to estimate and compare the level of salivary LDH in smokeless tobacco users with and without gingivitis.

In line with the current technology, a broadly accepted scale that measures habit in cigarette smokers was adapted for use with SLT users. The Fagerstrom Tolerance Questionnaire (FTQ) has been used worldwide in smoking cessation research.⁹ Heatherton and colleagues formed a 6-item scale that is closely associated with biochemical indices of heaviness of smoking with a reasonable level of internal consistency.¹⁰ Hence, in the present study Nicotine dependence was determined on the basis of Fagerstrom Nicotine Dependence Scale – Smokeless Tobacco (FTND-ST).

Tejashree Mantri et al.,¹¹ estimated levels of salivary LDH levels in habitual tobacco users as 125.19 ± 13.42 IU/L which was notably higher than the control group estimated as 86.12 ± 7.05 IU/L. Amanthi Ganapathi et al.,¹² studied the enzymatic biomarkers to evaluate periodontal severity in nominated patients with and without periodontal disease. Level of salivary LDH in control and individuals with periodontal disease was evaluated to be 292.60 ± 62.62 and 529.80 ± 88.95 respectively which was statistically significant. The study by Rashmi Kademadkal Javaraiah et al.,¹³ evaluated and found association between the proportion of salivary LDH in healthy individuals with tobacco users resulting in gradual rise in the levels of LDH from control to tobacco users. Increase in the LDH level was also reported with prolonged duration and frequency of the habit. Janet Moradi Haghgoo et al.,¹⁴ conducted a study to compare salivary lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels in individuals with periodontal disease and levels in individuals without periodontal disease. The mean LDH levels in the test and control groups were 1071.67 ± 731.004 and 550.91 ± 217.215 , respectively which was statistical significance with a P value < 0.05 .

In the present study we found increase in the mean value of Nicotine dependence score from periodontally healthy to gingivitis individuals as 4.41 ± 1.5 and 5.83 ± 1.5 as shown in Table 3. This finding was in agreement with the study by Jyoti Goyal et al.,¹⁵ who showed higher prevalence of periodontal disease among nicotine dependent individuals. When the effect of tobacco is considered, its duration, frequency, and its form will play a major role in causing its effect on the oral cavity. Our present study showed increase in periodontal health deterioration with increased nicotine dependence score which is in agreement with several studies. Dr. Sirjana Dahal et al.,¹⁶ showed in her study that, all the tobacco users having high nicotine dependence (20, 100%) due to tobacco smoking and moderate (32, 100%) to high dependence (19, 95%) due to tobacco chewing had significantly greater presence of periodontitis than those having low dependence.

Limitations:

Inadequate volume of the saliva sample collected, reduced sensitivity of salivary concentration of biomarkers, and early expiration of reagents used in the salivary biomarkers analysis affect the reaction and lead to a false-positive or false-negative results.

Conclusion:

Salivary lactate dehydrogenase promises to be a potential prognostic biomarker in early detection of periodontal disease as well as can contribute significantly in assessing the potential for malignant transformation with reasonable accuracy. The knowledge about the potential role of salivary biomarkers could play a key role in developing targeted interventions and treatments for individuals affected by smokeless tobacco use. Studies at a larger scale are needed to explore the full potential of salivary biomarkers in contemporary diagnosis.

References:

- [1] Nunn ME. Understanding the etiology of periodontitis: an overview of periodontal risk factors. *Periodontology* 2000. 2003 Jun; 32(1):11-23.
- [2] Calsina G, Ramon JM, Echeverria JJ. Effects of smoking on periodontal tissues. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2002; 29:771-6.
- [3] Stewart GG. A history of the medicinal use of tobacco 1492-1860. *Med Hist*. 1967; 11:228-68.
- [4] Changrani J, Cruz G, Kerr R, Katz R, Gany FM. Paan and gutka use in the United States: a pilot study in Bangladeshi and Indian-Gujarati immigrants in New York City. *Journal of immigrant & refugee studies*. 2006 Apr 26; 4(1):99-109.
- [5] Naresh CK, Rao SM, Shetty PR, Ranganath V, Patil AS, Anu AJ. Salivary antioxidant enzymes and lipid peroxidation product malondialdehyde and sialic acid levels among smokers and non-smokers with chronic periodontitis—A clinico-biochemical study. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*. 2019 Sep; 8(9):2960.
- [6] Giannobile VW. Salivary diagnostics for periodontal diseases. *J Am Dent Assoc* 2012; 143:6S-11S.
- [7] Kumar A, Pant MC, Singh HS, Khandelwal S. Assessment of the redox profile and oxidative DNA damage (8-OHdG) in squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck. *J Cancer Res Ther*. 2012; 8(2):254–259.
- [8] Weiner D, Khankin EV, Levy Y, Reznick AZ. Effects of cigarette smoke borne reactive nitrogen species on salivary alpha-amylase activity and protein modifications. *J Physiol Pharmacol*. 2009; 60:127-132.
- [9] Fagerstrom KO, Schneider NG. Measuring nicotine dependence: a review of the Fagerstrom Tolerance Questionnaire. *J Behav Med*. 1989 Apr; 12(2):159-82.
- [10] Jenifer HD, Bholra S, Kalburgi V, Warad S, Kokatnur VM. The influence of cigarette smoking on blood and salivary super oxide dismutase enzyme levels among smokers and nonsmokers-A cross sectional study. *J Tradit Complement Med*. 2015; 5:100-5.
- [11] Mantri T, Thete SG, Male V, Yadav R, Grover I, Adsure GR, Kulkarni D. Study of the role of salivary lactate dehydrogenase in habitual tobacco chewers, oral submucous fibrosis and oral cancer as a biomarker. *The Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*. 2019 Aug 1; 20(8):970-3.
- [12] Amanthi Ganapathi et al. Study Of Enzymatic Biomarkers To Evaluate Periodontal Severity. *J. Pharm. Sci. & Res*. 2016; 8(7):696-699.

- [13] Javaraiah RK, David CM, Namitha J, Tiwari R, Benakanal P. Evaluation of Salivary Lactate Dehydrogenase as a Prognostic Biomarker in Tobacco Users with and without Potentially Malignant Disorders of the Oral Cavity. *South Asian J Cancer*. 2020 Jun; 9(2):93-98.
- [14] Janet Moradi Haghgoo,¹ Sara Soheilifar,¹ Mohsen Bidgoli,¹ Neda Rastegarfar, Maral Saremi, and Samare Kafilzade. Comparison of Whole Salivary Lactate Dehydrogenase Level in Patients With and Without Periodontal Disease. *Avicenna J Dent Res*. 2016 December; 8(4):e29026.
- [15] Goyal J, Menon I, Singh RP, Gupta R, Sharma A, Bhagia P. Prevalence of periodontal status among nicotine dependent individuals of 35-44 years attending community dental camps in Ghaziabad district, Uttar Pradesh. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2019 Jul; 8(7):2456-2462.
- [16] Dahal S, Poudel P, Adhikari S. Nicotine Dependence and Periodontal Status among Tobacco Users in a Dental Hospital of Kathmandu Valley. *J Nepal Soc Perio Oral Implantol*. 2020 Jul-Dec; 4(8):78-82.